

THE GREETINGS IN DIFFERENT CULTURES

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Abstract. Greetings play an important role in every culture, serving as a way to show respect, establish rapport, and build relationships. Different cultures have unique greetings that reflect their values, traditions, and social norms. Understanding and respecting these cultural differences is essential when interacting with people from different backgrounds. In this article, we will explore some of the fascinating and diverse greetings practices around the world.

Key words: Greetings, culture, relationship, tradition, values, social norms, show respect, unique.

Annotatsiya. Salomlashish har bir madaniyatda muhim rol o'ynaydi, hurmat ko'rsatish, o'zaro munosabat o'rnatish va munosabatlarni o'rnatish uchun xizmat qiladi. Turli madaniyatlar o'zlarining qadriyatlarini, an'analari va ijtimoiy me'yorlarini aks ettiruvchi o'ziga xos tabriklarga ega. Ushbu madaniy farqlarni tushunish va hurmat qilish turli xil odamlar bilan muloqot qilishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolada biz butun dunyo bo'ylab salomlashishning qiziqarli va xilma-xil usullarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Salomlashish, madaniyat, Munosabatlar, an'analalar, qadriyatlar, ijtimoiy me'yorlar, hurmat ko'rsatish, noyob.

INTRODUCTION

Greeting someone you know is a vital part of courtesy and goodwill. All societies have some form of greeting. They are basic to civilized interaction. From the bowing of Japan to the handshakes of Western cultures, greetings serve as a window into the values and norms of each society, showcasing the richness and diversity of human interaction. By exploring and embracing these differences, individuals can foster greater understanding and appreciation for other cultures while building meaningful connections across borders. In many Western countries, a handshake is considered a warm, respectful greeting when meeting strangers or kicking off business meetings. But in other places in the world, not so much. Taking the time to learn how locals meet and greet is the first step to making a meaningful connection no matter where you are. From bumping noses in Qatar to bowing in Laos, here are 10 ways people greet each other in different countries and cultures. (Some of these gestures can be made without touching, which is especially helpful if you're currently opting for no-contact salutes to prevent the spread of coronavirus.)

1. Stick out your tongue

Tibet

Blame this greeting tradition on a really bad king. It all began with monks, who would stick out their tongues to show that they came in peace and weren't the reincarnation of a cruel 9th-century king named Lang Darma, who was known for having a black tongue. Needless to say, the greeting caught on.

2. Bump noses

Qatar, Yemen, Oman, United Arab Emirates

Want to demonstrate that you view a potential business contact as a peer? Forget shaking hands; instead, bring your nose in for a few friendly taps. Just remember: Sniffing isn't part of the equation.

3. Air kiss on the cheek

In Argentina, Chile, Peru, Mexico, São Paulo (Brazil) and Colombia, one air kiss is standard, whereas in Spain, Portugal, Paraguay, Italy, and cities like Paris and Québec, it's two. In Russia and Ukraine, three is the norm, and in some parts of France, it's up to four air kisses on alternating cheeks. To add a little more confusion to the mix, there are some tricky gender and relationship rules, too. In all of the countries mentioned, women air kiss women, and in most of them, men air kiss women, but only in Argentina do men routinely brush cheeks with other men who aren't relatives or romantic partners.

4. Rub noses (and sometimes foreheads)

New Zealand

If air kisses sound too intimate for your taste, try on hongi for size. This pressing together of forehead and nose is what New Zealand's indigenous Māori people call a "sharing of breath." The greeting signifies the sacred welcoming of a visitor into Māori culture and is used at pōwhiri (Māori welcoming ceremonies) although the honor requires an invitation and isn't extended to everyone.

5. Put your hand on your heart

Malaysia

It's very formal, but this traditional Malaysian greeting has a particularly lovely sentiment behind it. Take the opposite person's hands lightly in yours. Then, release the other person's hands and bring your own hands to your chest and nod slightly to symbolize goodwill and an open heart. It's polite for the other person to return the gesture. Note that men should wait for local women to extend a hand, and if they don't, a man should put a hand on his chest and give a slight nod.

6. Bow

Cambodia, India, Nepal, Laos, Thailand, and Japan

When it comes to bowing, the question isn't just when to take a bow, it's how to do it. In India, Nepal, Cambodia, Laos, and Thailand, press your palms together in an upward-pointing prayer position at heart level or higher, then bend your head slightly forward to take a bow. In India and Nepal, you might hear the phrase namaste uttered during this greeting; the Sanskrit term translates to bend or bow to you, and is considered a sign of respect and gratitude.

7. Revere your elders

Asia and Africa

Throughout Asia and Africa, honoring your elders is a given. This means greeting seniors and older folks before younger people and always using culture-specific titles and terms of respect upon first meeting. In the Philippines, locals have a particularly unique way of showing their reverence. They take an older person's hand and press it gently to their foreheads. In India, locals touch older people's feet as a show of respect. In Liberia, as well as among members of the Yoruba people in Nigeria, young people drop to one or both knees to honor their elders.

Greetings are an important part of social interactions in every culture, and they often reflect the values and customs of that society. Here are some examples of greetings in different cultures:

1. In Japan, a common greeting is "Konnichiwa," which means "hello" or "good afternoon." Bowing is also a common form of greeting in Japanese culture.
2. In India, people often greet each other with the word "Namaste," which means "I bow to you." The gesture involves pressing the palms together in front of the chest and bowing slightly.
3. In China, a common greeting is "Ni hao," which means "hello." Handshakes are also commonly used in business settings.
4. In Thailand, people greet each other by pressing their palms together in a prayer-like gesture called the "wai."
5. In Russia, it is customary to greet with a firm handshake and direct eye contact.

CONCLUSION

Greetings vary widely across different cultures and can reflect the values and customs of a particular society. In some cultures, greetings are formal and may involve bowing or shaking hands, while in others they are more casual and may involve hugs or kisses on the cheek. In some cultures, it is important to address someone by their title or last name, while in others first names are used. In many Eastern cultures, such as Japan and China, greetings are accompanied by bowing as a sign of respect. In Middle Eastern cultures, it is common to greet with a warm handshake and multiple kisses on the cheek. In Latin American countries, greetings are often accompanied by physical contact such as hugs or kisses on the cheek. In African cultures, greetings are an important part of social interaction and may involve lengthy exchanges of pleasantries.

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